

THE ORGANIZATION OF STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT STUDY ACTIVITIES TOGETHER WITH THE USE OF ICT AND TOOLS

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ANNOTATION

In the article, the criteria of ICTs and tools that can be used in organizing students' independent study activities in higher education institutions have been explored. It is determined the students' independent study activities are an individual, group, or collective activity and is implemented within the process of education under the condition of no pedagogy's direct involvement. It complies with the requirements of the curriculum and syllabus and is aimed at students' acquisition of some social experiences in line with the learning objectives of vocational training.

Keywords: *students' independent study activity, process of activity's organization, ICT, ICTs and tools.*

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida talabalarning mustaqil ta'lim faoliyatini tashkil etishda qo'llanilishi mumkin bo'lgan AKT va vositalar mezonlari o'rganilgan. Talabalarning mustaqil ta'lim faoliyati individual, guruh yoki jamoaviy faoliyat bo'lib, pedagogikaning bevosita ishtirokisiz ta'lim jarayonida amalga oshiriladi. U o'quv rejasi va o'quv rejasi talablariga javob beradi va o'quvchilarning kasb-hunar ta'limining o'quv maqsadlariga mos ravishda ba'zi ijtimoiy tajribalarni egallashiga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *talabalarning mustaqil ta'lim faoliyati, jarayoni faoliyatni tashkil etish, AKT, AKT va vositalar.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье исследованы критерии ИКТ и инструменты, которые могут быть использованы при организации самостоятельной учебной деятельности студентов в высших учебных заведениях. Определено, что самостоятельная учебная деятельность студентов является индивидуальной, групповой или коллективной деятельностью и реализуется в процессе обучения при условии отсутствия непосредственного участия педагога. Он соответствует требованиям учебного плана и программы и направлен на приобретение

учащимися определенного социального опыта в соответствии с учебными целями профессионального обучения.

Ключевые слова: *самостоятельная учебная деятельность студентов, процесс организации деятельности, ИКТ, ИКТ и средства.*

Introduction. The examination of the latest information and technological policies for the organization of students' independent study activities created the possibility to confine the means of realization of the leading forms of organization for this activity (independent and research work, lectures, consultations and nonformal education), to describe and classify the ICTs and tools that support the representation of teaching materials, electronic communication, mastering of learning material, monitoring of students' learning and cognitive activity, such as ones that serve for the sake of growth and support of automated training classes, systems of remote virtual education with segments of artificial intelligence, which implements the regulation of adaptive administration of learning and the organization of students' independent study activities.

Criteria for the practical organizing of students' independent study activities via the use of ICTs and tools are important. It is regarded that the organizing of independent study activities with the use ICTs tools is believed an efficacious if the learners gain a particular amount of understanding at the applicable general scientific and professional level, assembling the important features of their personality, necessary for additional intellectual and professional growth. At the same time, the autonomous study exercises have been carried out on the ground of self-management by learners and the systemic avoiding judged management by lecturers as well as rates of mental labour, sanitary and hygienic and ergonomic necessities in the application of ICTs have been taken into account. The significance of the organization of students' self-dependent study exercises can be evaluated by several criteria. The students' motives and motivation define their meaning, which is the primary factor of one's effectiveness, specifically in terms of when the classroom training has been lessened. Starting independently, based on their needs, the student has put forward a detailed goal. Therefore, the objective is being defined as a conscious need, as a marking of the desired result that is being produced in the student's movement towards the achievement of it¹. Thus, triggering the students' cognitive interests, prompting their innovative initiative, and the urge to perform the submitted learning tasks in a qualitative and timely manner, to master and apply for the sake of these most recent ICTs is the foremost urgent step in systematising an effective students' independent study activity². The next step is to construct content and an instrumental basis for independent study activities. This implicates, firstly, the construction of students'

teaching and methodological wisdom for the organization of autonomous learning, as well as strategies, techniques and skills for deciphering the set of educational tasks with the wide application of ICTs. In the end, the effectiveness of the functioning of such a system is evaluated by the educational, mental and privately significant products of students' independent study activities. In that way, based on the structure and content of the system of students' independent study activities, the criteria for its effective organizing are motivational, substantive, organizational and productive. At the same time, considering the general state of the effectiveness of the organization of the studied activities, one requires a separate study and investigates the technological ability criterion of the educational process. Thanks to it we could estimate the motivational provision of the students' and lecturers' functioning in the organization of independent study activities together with the use ICTs and tools; make diagnostic and appreciate the efficiency of the investigated process; design the content of independent study activity by way of a system of cognitive and practical tasks as well as an indicative basis and methods of their solution;

1. Volkova, N.P.: Independent work of students as a means of training future teachers for the implementation of vocational and pedagogical communication. *Humanitarnyi zhurnal* 3–4 (35–36), 159–165 (2007).

2. Bendera, I. M.: The theory and methods of future specialists in agricultural mechanization individual work in educational institutions. Dissertation, The Pedagogical education institute and adults' education APS of Ukraine (2009).

achieve algorithmically, optimality, integrity and controllability of the process organizing students' independent study activity with the use of ICT and tools; the amount the effectiveness and developmental nature of students' self-study and whatever³. Describing the level of efficiency in organizing students' independent study activity via the use of ICTs and tools we proceed from the features of educational activity as a process that can have different degrees of implementation and the subject of management. Therefore, taking into account the above-mentioned, we distinguish four levels, these are insufficient, critical, sufficient and proficiency. The examination of the latest information and technological policies for the organization of students' independent study activities created the possibility to confine the means of realization of the leading forms of organization for this activity (independent and research work, lectures, consultations and nonformal education), to describe and classify the ICTs and tools that support the representation of teaching materials, electronic communication, mastering of learning material, monitoring of students' learning and cognitive activity, such as ones that serve for the sake of growth and support of automated training classes, systems of remote virtual education with segments of artificial intelligence, which

implements the regulation of adaptive administration of learning and the organization of students' independent study activities.

In conclusion, Obviously, the nominal increase in the volume of students' independent work without introducing changes in the structure and content of the educational process has resulted in most cases in a decrease in cognitive motivation among students, impedes the development of important personality traits and characteristics, impacts on the specialists' competitiveness and their professional mobility, doesn't ensure appropriate evolution of students' abilities in learning throughout their life and doesn't allow them to master new technologies. In terms of information society researchers are seeing new wide perspectives in the active introduction of modern information and communication and network technologies,

3. Chernilevskii, D. V.: Didactic technologies in higher education. IuNITI, Moscow (2002). computer based technology, tools of transfer and exchange of information. At the same time the development and mass application of ICTs is seem to have caused significant changes in the informational and educational spheres of a higher education institution. Therefore, the introduction of a new structure, the latest ICT tools into the administration and self-management of the students' independent study activities requires investigation and research.

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3. Chernilevskii, D. V.: *Didactic technologies in higher education. IuNITI, Moscow (2002).*